

Linkage between Financial Inclusion and Economic Growth – A Theoretical Review

Ashu¹

ABSTRACT

Aim-The aim of the study is to review the past studies related to financial Inclusion and Economic Growth to find out whether if there is a relationship between the two.
Methodology-This is a theoretical paper based on secondary sources which include various research papers dealing with financial inclusion and economic growth for the period from 2014-2023.

Findings- Various studies on the topic has been studied in the past which indicate that there is a significant connection between financial Inclusion and Economic growth. Financial Inclusion have notable effect on economic growth in developing as well as in developed countries.

Practical implications-This research paper will be very beneficial to policymakers and they will initiate actions according to promote inclusive growth in long run.

Keywords: Financial Inclusion, Growth, Economy

INTRODUCTION

An efficient flow of money from lenders to borrowers back up by a sound financial system is required to boost the economy of developed as well as developing countries (McKinnon,1973).There should be a proper system that work towards build up a strong financial structure of country by mobilizing saving but statistics shows the worst situation where large number of population still not using any kind of financial services even in developed countries (Sharma,2016).Various steps have been taken by countries about how to include those who are outside the boundaries of financial system as it impedes economic development (Kempson,2006).Depending upon the

extent of financial exclusion in different countries, policymakers are designing pro strategies at different levels and committed towards their implementation. Financial exclusion is not able to access basic financial services by common man (Sinclair, 2001).Hence, financial inclusion is a way to include all from various parts of the society which not only enhance their standard of living but also helps to build a sound financial infrastructure which leads to economic growth and development. Literature shows that finance plays key role in reducing poverty, one of the main issue world is facing from more than a decade. As per United Nations, poverty is one of the greatest trouble that society face. Absence of financial inclusion leads

¹Assistant Professor (Commerce), Government College for Women, Shahzadpur

to increasing role on unorganised financial sector where a higher rate of interest was charged by the lender or land had to be mortgaged to meet their urgent needs which again create a burden and for them it became impossible to come out of vicious circle of poverty. The basic financial products and services provided to the community by Financial inclusion result in reducing poverty, financially deprived weaker section thus makes possible sustainable growth (Gupta et al,2014).It's a wide term which consist of banking and non-banking sectors and their services (Sethi and Acharya, 2018).It involve giving financial services either from banking or other channel in a convenient or cost effective way, by contrast we experienced problems both demand and supply side which require attention.

FINANCIAL INCLUSION IN INDIA

Financial Inclusion is an old phenomenon in India with its roots in 1960s when the licensing condition for opening bank outlets were simplified to provide banking services in unbanked zones as banking facilities was limited in large capitals only. First time Financial Inclusion was used in 2005 by Dr. Y. V. Reddy, Governor of RBI in which banks were advised to speed up their actions towards goal of inclusiveness. In 2006 to create a flexible path, RBI give permission to take help of other financial intermediaries such as micro institution, self help group (SHG) as they have easy access in rural area and they work towards unbanked population. Several committees were setup from time to time under the guidance of Dr. C. Rangarajan, in 2008 and formed another Committee on Comprehensive Financial Services considering Small Businesses and low-

income Households in 2014 to find out the problems associated and after investigation they reported that access to funds by the vulnerable group leads to upliftment of their standard of living resulting in reduction in poverty thus stimulates economic growth. In 2014, National level mission named “Pradhan Mantri Jan-DhanYojna” was introduced by then Prime Minister of India to increase number of bank accounts.This scheme was associated with number of additional benefits given to beneficiaries such as insurance, Rupay card, overdraft facilities, no minimum amount required etc. Over the period of time, as on 17 May, 2023 a total of 197193 crore account were opened and around 33 crore Rupay debit card were issued (pmjdy.gov.in). As per CRISIL (Credit Rating Information Services of India) Inclusive Report 2018, Financial Inclusion score of India has been improved significantly as it was 58 in 2016 as compared to 35.4 in 2009.

Fig 1: Composition of Financial Inclusion

Source: Report of the Rangarajan Committee on Financial Inclusion (2008)

Review of Literature

Several studies have been conducted in the past which confirm the link between FI and EG. Some have analysed that finance inclusion not only improved financial stability but also contributed to long-term economic growth. In this study literature has been analysed mainly with focus on financial Inclusion and its impact on economic growth, sustainable development.

STUDIES RELATED TO FINANCIAL INCLUSION AND ITS IMPACT ON GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT

Banerjee and Francis (2014) Investigated the effect of financial inclusion on social development by developing an index for 24 states of India using UNDP methodology of HDI creation on the dimensions of banking penetration, banking availability, and usage of banking services. Kerala, Maharashtra, and Karnataka were the top three states and found direct relationship between financial inclusion and the human development index and indicated that financial inclusion significantly reduces poverty.

Patil and Kadam (2014) Examined the concept of economic dimension of sustainable development in general, and perspective of Environment economics in particulars for the period of eight years 2000-01 to 2009-10. It concluded that India is moving towards attainment of sustainable development goals but there are still many factors like low self-sufficiency, fluctuation in economic growth rate, less rate of investment, on which more work should be done for achieving high level of sustainability.

Another study by Arun and Kamath (2015) shed light on various practices adopted by thirty countries using Microscope data for improving financial inclusion as it is a matter of concern for all. It was observed that countries in the middle scale focus on one or few parameters. Some countries try to increase bank penetration like Jan Dhan Yojana in India started in 2014, some rely on mobile phone for banking services like Kenya where majority population opt for electronic payment.

Sharma, D (2016) Author examined the association between financial inclusion and economic growth by taking various dimensions related to banking system for the period 2004 to 2013. It was observed that role of banking system in creating a sound financial infrastructure especially in developing economies. Studies show that a strong banking system leads to availability of credit that result in long run economic growth. It found that there is a positive association between financial inclusion & economic growth especially in banking penetration, availability of banking service.

Usha and Johnson (2016) Researcher in this paper identified changes in indicators of financial inclusion from 2011 to 2014 in some leading economies. And an attempt is made to understand the bond between Gross National Income and indicators of financial inclusion. Study showed that there was a positive connection between financial inclusion and economic growth in terms of mobilising saving, capital formation, and better standard of living.

Kim (2016) examined the role of financial inclusion in reducing income inequality and promoting economic growth and explained

the adverse impact of financial exclusion on the growth of the society by taking data of forty countries of OECD and EU for the period 2004 to 2011. The countries were divided into high- and low-income groups according to GDP and according to non-performing assets as high and low fragility countries to reach the conclusion that financial inclusion reduces income inequality and improves the level of economic growth.

Iqbal and Sami (2017) The study was conducted to analyse the present status of financial inclusion in India and the role that it plays for the removal of hurdles for which data have collected from various secondary sources for the period from 2007 to 2014. It was analysed that there is a positive impact of number of bank outlets and credit deposit ratio on GDP whereas negative impact of ATMs on Indian GDP.

Uddin et al. (2017) Explored the extent of financial inclusion in Bangladesh by collecting data from 25 banks for the period from 2005 to 2014. Panel data regression method was used in the study to identify the parameters from demand and supply side affecting financial inclusion. size of bank, efficiency in operational activities, and average interest rates, education and dependency ratio some of the factors which were discussed. The article suggested that financial inclusion can be improved by lower the rate of interest and promoting human development.

Rajasekaran (2018) Based on the secondary sources, this article explained the efforts initiated by the Reserve Bank of India and Government of India to promote financial inclusion and discussed different challenges come in the way of

financial inclusion in India. It was found that financial inclusion directly affects the country's economy's development. Insufficient financial literacy programmes, unstable profits negatively impact India's rate of growth of level of financial Inclusion.

Kim et al. (2018) Studied the connection between financial inclusion and economic growth with focus on fifty-five member economies of OIC (Organisation of Islamic Cooperation). The hypothesis was tested using panel vector auto regression and Granger causality tests. It is observed that economic growth and financial inclusion are bidirectionally related. Therefore, a higher standard of living can be achieved by the financial inclusion and thus reducing poverty.

Siddiqui (2018) Pointed out that financial inclusion play an significant role in development of the country but still there are various hurdles which need to be settled as the ratio of number of populations having no account is higher in India as compared to other countries. It plays a positive role towards socio-economic development, eliminating poverty, inclusive growth of a country so, it is considered as one of the main goal to achieve by many of the leading economies.

Raza, et al. (2019) The authors pointed out a positive connection between the level of FI and economic development in Pakistan for the year 2010-2015 using regression and correlation analysis. In detail, the number of bank accounts have a positive relationship with human development index (HDI) whereas the amount of ATMs reveals a negative relationship.

Datta and Singh (2019) Analysed the

various dimensions of financial inclusion across developed and developing countries for the time 2011 to 2014. Principal component method along with pooled OLS with clustered standard error regression model has been used to calculate the availability, access and usage and explain different factors affecting financial inclusion among various countries of the world. It was found there is wide range of gap in financial inclusion level in different countries. developed countries achieve good ranking as compared to less developed in terms of providing banking services. Also, there was positive relation between Human Development index and financial inclusion due to increase in income, better education, and health.

Dahiya and Kumar (2020) focused on inclusive finance as a tool to achieve sustainable development. Poverty is a matter of concern in most of the countries including India where twenty two percent of population living below poverty line. Financial inclusion helps in minimising poverty and building strong financial infrastructure by including the excluded population into the formal structure.

Malhotra (2020) In this paper she observed that financial inclusion plays a key part in inclusive growth and policy makers make strategy to successfully implement financial inclusion. Study concluded that financial penetration encourages economic growth and execution of focused financial inclusion programs by government becomes imperative to achieve holistic growth. Also found that a well organised financial system is required for economic growth but developing countries face challenges which limit the spread of financial services and products to masses.

Ain et al. (2020) The study examined the effect of FI, entrepreneurship and institutions on economic growth. For the purpose, data of 33 developing countries were taken over time for the period 2004-2016 and GMM was used to find out the impact of these variables on economic growth. Empirical results show that financial inclusion has positive effect on growth of economy.

Sikarwar (2020) Examined the relationship between economic growth, household debt and financial inclusion and how these variables are interconnected and impact positively or negatively on development in India. This paper observed that there is high rate of increase debt (household and firm debt) in India which require attention of policy makers. Increasing use of debt and loans by stakeholders disrupt the financial system. It is found that household debt & economic growth have a negative connection.

Vaid, et al. (2020) Examined the key determinants such as Outreach, Penetration, access, technology, literacy, income, Perceived benefits that helped in providing access of financial product and services to low income rural population in Raipur, Chhattisgarh. It was found that trust, income, benefits of using financial services and technology had positive impact on financial inclusion.

Nizam et al. (2020) Investigates the influence of financial inclusiveness on economic growth in few nations. It is found that there is a nonlinear relationship between financial inclusiveness and economic growth.

Prakash (2020) Mentioned that financial inclusion is one of the key aspects for growth of country by ensuring access of financial services by unreached masses at

reasonable cost. Financial inclusion plan was designed by the RBI to boost inclusion for which implementation was carried out in two phases. Unbanked villages were identified and strategies were made how to involve them into mainstream. Proper guidelines were issued to banks to look after the matter. Study used secondary sources to evaluate the development of FI in India. It was found that RBI provided various relaxations to banks to faster the process of inclusiveness.

Ahmed and Singel (2020) investigated the increasing role of FI in growth and poverty alleviation and explained the benefits of high level of inclusiveness in any country. Role of banks is crucial they need to use innovative products to improve financial inclusion strategies. Also explained the role of stakeholders like self-help group, banks and microfinance institution and challenges like financial illiteracy, lack of access to services, language barrier faced by them to implement successfully inclusion.

Arora and Kumar (2021) Financial inclusion and human development have a long-term causally related bidirectionally relationship. In India, government schemes and actions should be adopted to accelerate the process of financial inclusion, which play a crucial part in human development.

Cicchiello (2021) analysed the nexus among the index of financial inclusion and development variables like GDP, literacy rate, unemployment rate by collecting data on 42 countries in Asia and Africa for the period 2000-2019. Result showed that inequality in wealth distribution, gender-based discrimination negatively affects poor countries but Gross Domestic Product is a leading indicator of financial

inclusion.

Chiad (2021) examined the nexus among financial inclusion (FI), trade openness, human development and GDP growth in Algeria. It showed that these variables have a progressive and major impact on economic growth, thereby confirming the strength of the finance-growth connections.

Niaz (2021) This paper discussed the role of Microfinance institutions in providing finance to excluded people. These institutions play a key role in bringing left out into mainstream, creating financial infrastructure and moving towards sustainable development goals. It concluded that Microfinance institutions contribute positively towards reducing poverty leading to sustainable livelihood.

Amari and Anis (2021) Identified the significant factors affecting possession of a bank account, savings, and borrowing behaviour with Probit model on employed data of Tunisia from Global Findex, 2017. Empirical results suggested that gender, age, literacy, income, type of area, and employment status are key indicators of financial inclusion. The study concluded that financial inclusion could be used as a channel for economic development in Tunisia and suggested that to make the financial inclusion drive successful the population must be financial literate.

Zhang (2022) Paper discussed the linkage between financial inclusion, non-performing loans (NPLs), and economic growth of twenty one OCED (Organization for Economic Corporation and Development) for the period ranging between 2004 to 2017 using dynamic panel estimation by taking variables from both demand and supply side. It concluded that financial Inclusion contributes

optimistically to economic growth by minimising Non-Performing Assets. The increase in incapability of customer to repay loans result in strict monetary policy which act as blockage in smooth money supply.

Liu (2022) Paper studied the relationship between financial inclusion, economic growth and the environmental quality of OBOR nations. It was found that supply-side financial inclusion indicators like ATMS and branches have positively significant impact financial inclusion and supply or demand side variables put a clear influence on the CO2 emissions in OBOR countries. **Saha (2023)** analysed the influence of financial inclusion on growth of the economy in 104 developing nations for the years 2004 to 2019 using dynamic panel estimation technique. It was concluded that it helps in development in economies through providing opportunities for low-income people. With access to financial product and services by the weaker group, it enhances economic activities which leads to economic development.

ECONOMIC GROWTH AND FINANCIAL INCLUSION

Financial inclusion plays a vital role in promoting economic growth by offering everyone with access to financial services. Here are different ways in which FI impact the economic growth.

1. Increased saving and investment: FI enables individuals to save money securely and access various financial tools such as savings accounts, fixed deposits, and investment opportunities. As people accumulate savings, they can invest in productive assets and businesses, which, in turn, stimulates economic growth.

2. Access to credit and capital: Financial

inclusion ensures that all should have access to affordable credit and capital. This allows industrialists to expand their businesses, invest in technology and infrastructure, and create job opportunities. By simplifying access to credit, financial inclusion fosters entrepreneurial activity and innovation, driving economic growth.

3. Minimized Poverty: Financial inclusion has the power to lift people out of poverty by providing them with the tools and resources to improve their standard of living. It allows marginalized individuals to access financial services, build assets, and engage in income-generating activities. As more people escape poverty, overall consumer spending increases, leading to economic expansion.

4. Increased consumption and economic related activities: When individuals have access to formal financial services, they can more effectively manage their income, smooth consumption patterns, and plan for the future. This stability and predictability in personal finances lead to increased consumer spending, which drives demand and economic activity.

5. Create jobs: FI facilitates entrepreneurship by providing access to capital and financial resources to start and grow businesses. As entrepreneurship flourishes, it leads to job creation and employment opportunities, contributing to economic growth and reducing unemployment rates.

6. Financial sector development: FI encourages the development and expansion of the financial sector. As more individuals and businesses participate in formal financial systems, there is increased demand for banking services, insurance, investment products, and other financial

tools. This drives innovation, competition, and efficiency within the financial sector, contributing to overall economic growth.

7. Strengthened resilience and risk management: Financial inclusion allows individuals and businesses to better manage financial risks and shocks. By having access to insurance products, savings, and credit, they can cope with unexpected events such as illness, natural disasters, or economic downturns. This resilience enhances overall economic stability and fosters long-term growth.

CONCLUSION

Financial inclusion promotes economic growth by providing easy access to credit, financial services, and investment opportunities. It empowers individuals, reduces poverty, stimulates entrepreneurship, boosts consumer spending, and strengthens overall economic resilience. By enabling a broader participation in the financial system, FI contributes to inclusive and sustainable economic growth.

REFERENCE

1. Amari, M., & Anis, J. (2021). Exploring the impact of socio-demographic characteristics on financial inclusion: Empirical evidence from Tunisia. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 48(9), 1331-1346. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSE-08-2020-0527>.
2. Arora, N., & Kumar, N. (2021). Does financial inclusion promote human development? Evidence from India. *Jindal Journal of Business Research*, 10(2), 163-184.
3. Arun, T., & Kamath, R. (2015). Financial inclusion: Policies and practices. *IIMB Management Review*, 27(4), 267-287.
4. Banerjee, S., & Francis, G. (2014). Financial inclusion and social development. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 2321(3418), 13-18.
5. Chiad, F., Aouissi, A., & Lahsasna, A. (2021). Financial Market Inclusion and Economic Growth: Evidence from Algeria. *Empirical Economics Letters*, 20(10).
6. Cicchiello, A. F., Kazemikhasragh, A., Monferrá, S., & Girón, A. (2021). Financial inclusion and development in the least developed countries in Asia and Africa. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 10(1), 1-13.
7. Dahiya, S., & Kumar, M. (2020). Linkage between financial inclusion and economic growth: An empirical study of the emerging Indian economy. *Vision*, 24(2), 184-193.
8. Datta, S. K., & Singh, K. (2019). Variation and determinants of financial inclusion and their association with human development: A cross-country analysis. *IIMB Management Review*, 31(4), 336-349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2019.07.013>
9. Gupta, A., Chotia, V., & Rao, N. M. (2014). Financial inclusion and human development: A state-wise analysis from India. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 11(5), 1-24.
10. Iqbal, B. A., & Sami, S. (2017). Role of banks in financial inclusion in India. *Contaduría y administración*, 62(2), 644-656.
11. Kempson, E. 2006. Policy level

- response to financial inclusion in developed countries: Lessons for developing countries. Paper presented at the Conference on Access to Finance, Washington, DC, May 30-31.
12. Kim, D. W., Yu, J. S., & Hassan, M. K. (2018). Financial inclusion and Economic growth in OIC countries. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 43, 1-14
 13. Kim, J. H. (2016). A study on the effect of financial inclusion on the relationship between income inequality and economic growth. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 52(2), 498-512.
 14. Kumar Vaid, Y., Singh, V., & Sethi, M. (2020). Determinants of successful financial inclusion in low-income rural population. *The Indian Economic Journal*, 68(1), 82-100.
 15. Le, T. H., Chuc, A. T., & Taghizadeh-Hesary, F. (2019). Financial inclusion and its impact on financial efficiency and sustainability: Empirical evidence from Asia. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 19(4), 310-322.
 16. Le, T. H., Chuc, A. T., & Taghizadeh-Hesary, F. (2019). Financial inclusion and its impact on financial efficiency and sustainability: Empirical evidence from Asia. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 19(4), 310-322.
 17. Malhotra, N (2020). Financial Inclusion and Economic Growth: Case of Emerging Asian Economies. Lal Bahadur Shastri Institute of Management, Delhi, WP/ August2020/16.
 18. Mckinnon, R.I. (1973), *Money and Capital in Economic Development*, Brookings Institution Press, Washington, DC.
 19. Mouna, A., & Jarboui, A. (2021). Understanding the link between government cashless policy, digital financial services and socio-demographic characteristics in the MENA countries. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*. Advance Online Publication.
 20. Niaz, M. U. (2021). Socio-Economic development and sustainable development goals: a roadmap from vulnerability to sustainability through financial inclusion. *Economic Research-Ekonomskalstraživanja*, 1-33.
 21. Nizam, R., Karim, Z. A., Rahman, A. A., & Sarmidi, T. (2020). Financial inclusiveness and economic growth: New evidence using a threshold regression analysis. *Economic research-Ekonomskaistraživanja*, 33(1), 1465-1484.
 22. Patil, J. S., & Kadam, P. J. (2014). Sustainable Development in Indian Economic Perspective. *Journal of Economic an Sustainable Development*, 5(19).
 23. Perrin, C., & Weill, L. (2022). No Man, No Cry? Gender Equality in Access to Credit and Financial Stability. *Finance Research Letters*, 102694.
 24. Prakash, M. P. (2020). Financial Inclusion Plan-Progress and Prospects. *IJRAR-International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, E-ISSN, 2348-1269.
 25. Raza, M. Tang, J. Rubab, S. & Wen, X. (2019). Determining the nexus between financial inclusion and economic development in Pakistan. *Journal of Money Laundering Control*,

- 22 (2), 195-209. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMLC-12-2017-0068>
26. Sharma, D. (2016). Nexus between financial inclusion and economic growth: Evidence from the emerging Indian economy. *Journal of financial economic policy*.
27. Siddiqui, A. U. (2018). Financial Inclusion in India-"A Catalyst for Sustainable Economic Growth. *International Journal of Management and Applied Science*, 4(2), 61-68.
28. Sikarwar, T., Goyal, A., & Mathur, H. (2020). Household debt, financial inclusion, and economic growth of India: is it alarming for India?. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 10(2), 229-248.
29. Silue, T. (2021). *Financial Inclusion and Economic Growth: Evidence in the Digital Environment of Developing Countries* (No. hal-03281843). HAL.
30. Uddin, A., Chowdhury, M. A. F., & Islam, M. N. (2017). Determinants of financial inclusion in Bangladesh: Dynamic GMM & quantile regression approach. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 51(2), 221-237.
31. ul Ain, N., Sabir, S., & Asghar, N. (2020). Financial inclusion and economic growth: Empirical evidence from selected developing economies. *Review of Economics and Development Studies*, 6(1), 179-203.
32. Usha, A. A., & Johnson, B. (2016). Is Financial Inclusion Growth Significant? *Amity Journal of Management Research*. 1(1), (1-15)
33. Zhang, P., Zhang, M., Zhou, Q., & Zaidi, S. A. H. (2022). The Relationship Among Financial Inclusion, Non-Performing Loans, and Economic Growth: Insights From OECD Countries. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13
34. Data Available from Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (<https://www.pmjdy.gov.in>).